

A Study on Microalbuminuria amongst Hypertensive Patients Attending a Tertiary Care Hospital of Tripura, North East Region**Das Sutapa¹, Roy Dipanwita², Pal Sanjoy Rudra³, Pal Partha Sarathi⁴, Sarkar Parimal Chandra⁵**¹MD, Medical Officer, IGM Hospital, P.O. Agartala, Tripura²MD, SR, Dept of Biochemistry Agartala Govt. Medical College, Agartala & GBP Hospital, P.O. Kunjavan, Agartala, Tripura³MD (Community Medicine), State Program Officer, NHM, Agartala, Tripura⁴MD, Associate Professor, Dept of Biochemistry, Agartala Govt. Medical College & GBP Hospital, P.O. Kunjavan, Agartala, Tripura⁵MD, Associate Professor, Dept of Medicine, Agartala Govt. Medical College & GBP Hospital, P.O. Kunjavan, Agartala, Tripura

Received: 25-08-2024 / Revised: 23-09-2024 / Accepted: 26-10-2024

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Hypertension (HTN) is regarded as a silent killer and if not diagnosed earlier and treated properly, it can cause many complications. Hypertensive nephropathy or renal disease occurs as a result of uncontrolled high blood pressure. Microalbuminuria is the earliest marker of hypertensive nephropathy. Microalbuminuria is associated with certain complications like cardiac complications and kidney disease. Recent advancements in diagnostic modalities for microalbuminuria have shown that urinary excretion of albumin is more in hypertensive patients as compared to subjects with normal blood pressure

Aim: To assess the Microalbuminuria amongst hypertensive patients attending at a Tertiary Care Hospital of Tripura.

Materials and method: In this cross-sectional study total 120 hypertensive patients were enrolled attending at the Medicine OPD of the AGMC & GBP Hospital, Agartala, Tripura.

Result: Microalbuminuria was found among 38% of the study population. Frequency of Microalbuminuria was increased with the increasing in age, duration and severity of hypertension. Microalbuminuria starts appearing well before the elevation of serum creatinine.

Conclusion: Early screening to detect microalbuminuria in early stages will help to initiate appropriate treatment regimen to arrest kidney damage and prevent the risk of complications and thus improvement in prognosis.

Keywords: Hypertension, Creatinine, Screening, Microalbuminuria.

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Introduction

Hypertension (HTN) is the most common cardiovascular disorder in the world, affecting nearly 1 billion people worldwide in 2000 and this is predicted to increase to 1.56 billion by 2025. [1,2] HTN causes 7.1 million deaths annually worldwide. [3] Hypertension, also known as high blood pressure (BP), is defined as systolic blood pressure (SBP) of 140 mmHg or greater or a diastolic blood pressure (DBP) of 90 mmHg or greater or taking antihypertensive medication [4]

It is difficult to understand the exact cause of hypertension as the complex interaction of genes and environmental factors lead to hypertension. More than 1/10th of Indian population is affected by HTN on annual basis. [5] Hypertension which has been recognized as a major health burden, plays a

very important role in developing various diseases, particularly acts as a major risk factor for stroke, cardiovascular disease and end-stage renal disease. Hypertension, even though if it is in asymptomatic state can lead to different types of Target Organ Damage (TOD). Left Ventricular Hypertrophy (LVH), retinopathy, microalbuminuria (MA) and cognitive dysfunction occur early in the natural course of hypertensive disease; while stroke, heart attack, renal failure etc. are usually a result of long-standing uncontrolled hypertension. [6]

The relationship between the blood pressure and kidney has a very complex relationship and each may adversely affect the other, thus hypertension is one of the most important causes of end stage renal disease. [7] It was estimated that 1 lakhs patient

developed End Stage Renal Disease (ESRD) every year in India. [8] In the hypertension, chronic kidney failure may slowly occur with few signs and symptoms in the early stages. If kidney damage can be detected in early stage it can prevent the progression to end stage renal disease.

A significant proportion of hypertensive population shows microalbuminuria as it is one of the earliest markers of renal injury and vascular dysfunction. As the overall burden of kidney disease increases, there is a need for increased screening, early identification and management to prevent adverse outcomes from the disease progresses.

In the diagnosis and management of kidney disease among people with hypertension and diabetes urinary albumin excretion has assumed a central role. [9]

MA which is the earliest marker of hypertensive and diabetic nephropathy and equally important observation is that MA is reversible to interventions aimed at tight control of blood pressure and blood sugar. [10] Microalbuminuria (MA) which can be defined as the urinary albumin excretion level that are below the usual limit of detection by qualitative testing, but above normal level, can be identified by simple measures, such as the urinary albumin to creatinine ratio (ACR) in untimed urine samples.

Microalbuminuria is an index of increased renal endothelial permeability and diffuse endothelial dysfunction. [11,12] From this perspective, this study has been undertaken to assess the microalbuminuria in hypertensive subjects attending Agartala Government Medical College (AGMC) and G. B. Pant Hospital. Implication of this study is highlighted at the detection of early stage of the kidney damage amongst hypertensive adults which is very much helpful for the management and better outcome.

Materials and Method

This was an observational study, conducted at Agartala Government Medical College, Tripura, India after due approval by the Institutional Ethical Committee (Ref.No.F.4(5-244)/AGMC/Academic/IEC Certificate/2021/7157 Dated 2nd June 2021). The study period was one and one half years from July 2021 to December 2022. Total 120 patients were included in the study.

Inclusion criteria:

1. Adult's patients who had fulfill the following criteria:
2. Hypertension criteria as per JNC-8 classification. [13]

Those who were known case of Hypertension ≥ 2 years, age ≥ 20 years to ≤ 60 years and willing to participate in the study were included in this study.

Exclusion criteria: Patients were excluded if they had one or more of the following diseases:

1. Cardiovascular disease.
2. Kidney disease.
3. Cerebrovascular disease.
4. Diabetes mellitus.
5. Muscular dystrophy.
6. Pregnancy.
7. Macroalbuminuria.

All the subjects were enrolled after obtaining written informed consent.

Detailed history was taken from all the participants with emphasis on duration of hypertension. Personal history regarding smoking, tobacco chewing, alcohol intake and diet (veg/non- veg/mixed) was also recorded. Thorough physical examination was performed on each patient.

Measurement of BP was conducted in a sitting position and started after a resting phase of at least 5 minutes. SBP and DBP were measured with mercury sphygmomanometer 2 times on the left arm with a break of 3 min between measurements. The averages of two readings were recorded.

Collection of blood sample

Under aseptic measures, 6 ml of blood was drawn preferably from the antecubital vein using a sterile needle and syringe. After collection, blood sample were kept in the prefixed containers (fluoride, EDTA, & clot activator container) and then the sample were allowed to clot at room temperature and then serum was separated by centrifugation and accordingly proper labeling including coding was done.

Whenever possible, analysis of the test was done immediately. In case, when there was delay, the aliquots of the sample were stored at 2-8°C until analysis.

Collection of urine sample

Patients were asked to collect the first voided early morning mid-stream urine sample in a sterile sealed container and to avoid exercise prior to urine collection. In women urine samples were collected during the non-menstrual phase of their cycle.

Study Procedure

Estimation of urine microalbumin was done by antigen antibody reaction with end point method. [14] Urine Creatinine was estimated by Enzymatic method. [15] Subsequently, microalbuminuria (MA) was assessed by urine albumin creatinine ratio (ACR) [16] ACR values between 30-300mg/gm of creatinine constituted microalbuminuria for the study purpose.

Statistical analysis: Data entry and analysis was performed using SPSS version 26.0 on Windows

PC. Categorical data were presented with the help of text, tables etc. Descriptive statistics like mean, standard deviation, frequency, percentage were used. Chi-square test was used for categorical variables for testing the significance of association between two or more risk factors. Student t-test for testing the significance of difference between two

means were used and ANOVA was used for continuous variables.

Pearson correlation was used for correlating biochemical markers and p-value less than 0.05 were considered statistically significant.

Result

Table 1: Gender Distribution among the study participants

Gender	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Male	80	67
Female	40	33
Total	120	100

Table 2: Distribution of study subjects among different age category

Age in Yrs	Frequency	Percentage (%)
20-30	4	3
31-40	11	10
41-50	40	33
51-60	65	54
Total	120	100

Table 3: Frequency of Microalbuminuria among the study population

Albuminuria status	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Normoalbuminuria (NA)	74	62
Microalbuminuria	46	38
Total	120	100

Frequency of microalbuminuria among the 120 hypertensive subjects is 38%.

Table 4: Microalbuminuria status among male and female

	Normoalbuminuria	Microalbuminuria	Total
Male	49	31	80
Female	25	15	40
Total	74	46	120
p value 0.894			

Frequency of microalbuminuria among male and female shows that among the total 80 male and 40 female hypertensive patients frequency of microalbuminuria are 31 (38.75%) and 15 (37.5%) respectively.

Table 5: Comparison of different variables among the microalbuminuria and Normoalbuminuria

Variable	Normoalbuminuria (mean± SD)	Microalbuminuria (mean ± SD)	p value	Significance
Age in years	48.16±7.4	53.91±5.8	<0.001	Highly Significant
SBP in mmHg	144.26±7.66	151.61±7	<0.001	Highly Significant
DBP in mmHg	88.95±5.1	90.39±5.8	0.156	Not Significant
Serum Creatinine	1.04± 0.35	1.32± 0.63	0.002	Significant

Comparison of mean±SD of systolic and diastolic blood pressure among the microalbuminuria and normoalbuminuria groups shows statistically significant higher mean systolic blood pressure among the hypertensive patients who had microalbuminuria

compare to those who had normoalbuminuria. Whereas there is no significant difference in diastolic blood pressure among these two groups. Serum creatinine is higher in hypertensive patients who microalbuminuria.

Table 6: Distribution of albuminuria status according to the duration of hypertension

		Albuminuria		Total
		Normoalbuminuria	Microalbuminuria	
Hypertension duration in years	≤ 10	55 (45.8%)	18(15%)	73
	>10	19(15.8%)	28(23.4%)	47
Total		74	46	120
p value <0.0001				

Table 7: Correlation coefficient (r) between the ACR and different variables

	Correlation coefficient (r)	P value
SBP	0.468	<0.0001
DBP	0.093	0.314
Duration of Hypertension	0.618	<0.0001

Table 8: Serum creatinine level among the study participants

Serum Creatinine	No of study participants	Percentage
≤ 1.4	104	86.7
> 1.4	16	13.3

The association between the microalbuminuria and the duration of hypertension was studied. All the study population were divided among two groups- those who had hypertension duration ≤ 10 years and those who had hypertension duration > 10 years. Microalbuminuria was found among the 18 (15%) of the study population who had hypertension ≤ 10 yrs whereas 28 (23.4%) of the study population with hypertension duration > 10 years had microalbuminuria with a p value < 0.0001 which is highly significant.

Discussion

Hypertension is one of the most important global health challenges due to its prevalence and causing burden worldwide. Hypertension is strongly associated with structural and functional damage of kidneys as well as other organs resulting in the development of cardiovascular disease and chronic kidney disease. [17,18] Ultimately it leads to premature morbidity and mortality.

Although, hypertension is often asymptomatic, it may unnoticeably affect kidneys causing microalbuminuria. Under normal condition, albumin which is filtered through the renal glomeruli, retrieved by the renal proximal tubular cells from the renal tubular lumen and enter in the peritubular blood microcirculation. The filtered albumin that cannot be retrieved by the proximal tubular cells, undergoes lysosomal degradation into small peptide fragments. Whenever there is an increased pressure load from an elevated aortic pulse pressure, an increased peripheral resistance and an augmented volume load from increased flow pulsation which could alter the renal hemodynamic and consequently damage the renal microvasculature. Therefore, the albumin is filtered to an extent that exceeds the retrieval capacity of the proximal tubules. Moreover, the elevated angiotensin II and transforming growth factor-β1 in hypertension could disturb the lysosomal degradation pathway and consequently lead to albuminuria.[19]

Male and female distribution among the study participants are 67% and 33% respectively (table 1) which are very much similar with the study conducted by the Papaiah Nirmal Pudota et al. [20] where 66% of the study subjects were male and 34% were female. This may be due to the higher

prevalence of hypertension among male compared to the female.

Urine albumin excretion upto 30 mg/day is considered normal. Microalbuminuria (MA) is defined as persistent elevation of albumin in the urine, of 30-300 mg/day (20-200 microg/min). These values are less than the values detected by routine urine dipstick testing, which does not become positive until protein excretion exceeds 300-500 mg/day. Among nondiabetic patients with essential hypertension MA is associated with higher blood pressures. [21]

In the present study prevalence of microalbuminuria among the hypertensive subjects are 38% (table 3) which is similar to the findings seen in the study conducted by the Kothari S et al [22] and RK Sabharwal et al [23] where microalbuminuria was detected in 34% and 33.3% of hypertensive subjects respectively. However, this figure is different from the study conducted by Akinsola et al.[24] and Salim S A et al. [25] where they found the prevalence of microalbuminuria was 17.4% and 68% respectively.

Variations found in prevalence of microalbuminuria among the hypertensive patients in different studies could be due to the different criteria used in selection, differences in the methods used for detecting microalbuminuria, the severity of hypertension, different age, population and ethnicity.

The mean age among the microalbuminuria group is higher (53.91±5.8) compare to those having normoalbuminuria (48.16±7.4) with the p value of < 0.001. Maximum prevalence of microalbuminuria has been found in 51-60 age group (Table 2). These findings are similar to the findings seen in the study conducted by Stalin D J et al. [26] Wachtell Ketel [27] and PN Pudota et al. [20] Pragati Bhole et al. [28] where they reported the association of microalbuminuria with increasing age. The higher prevalence of microalbuminuria in the elderly in this study can be related to the pathological processes in the kidney. Histological changes like glomerulosclerosis, tubular atrophy, interstitial fibrosis, and arteriolar sclerosis have found to be increase with higher age even in the absence of hypertension and diabetes.[29] Thus the prevalence of microalbuminuria increases with age.[30] People with higher SBP was more likely to have microal-

buminuria (Table 5) in our study which is similar to the findings of a study conducted by Kothari S et al.[22]

In Table 7, statistically significant positive correlation (r value is 0.618) was found between hypertension duration and microalbuminuria in our study which is evident from the findings that the maximum number of the hypertensive subjects who had microalbuminuria had longer duration i.e >10 yrs (Table 6). This findings is in accordance to the some studies conducted by Salim S et al [25] and Navya D et al [31] where they found that with increasing in the duration of hypertension microalbuminuria was also increased.

In this study, serum creatinine exceeding 1.4mg/dl was found in 13.3 % hypertensive patients (Table 8) that means if it is taken as a measure for renal disease then only 13.3 % hypertensive patients are showing renal dysfunction. But microalbuminuria starts well before the increase in serum creatinine. So, it is stated by a study done by Pruijm MT et al [32] that the presence of microalbuminuria in early stage of essential hypertension can be taken as an important predictor for progression of renal disease.

Limitations

The study was focused on the screening of the participants for the presence of microalbuminuria, which is not commonly practiced in our state, was the main strength of the study. The first limitation of the present study is the small sample size and therefore larger studies are recommended to gather better correlation between microalbuminuria and hypertension. A cross-sectional study design, which did not show the exact cause and effect relationship of the disease and factors, was also another limitation of the study.

Conclusion

Early screening of hypertensive patients for microalbuminuria and prompt treatment of such individual may help to reduce the burden of chronic kidney disease and cardiovascular disease in the community. So, microalbuminuria should be tested routinely in hypertensive patients because its appearance, progression to proteinuria, or regression to normal albuminuria can be correlated with a higher or lower risk of coronary heart disease, stroke, or peripheral vascular disease.

Therefore, urinary screening for microalbuminuria at least once in a year in every hypertensive patient improves the targeting of primary prevention and results in reduction in target organ damage. Current challenges therefore should preclude the inclusion of microalbuminuria in the routine management of hypertensive patients as the care of end stage kidney disease is very expensive and, in many circumstances, unaffordable, while early intervention may

retard the progression of kidney disease.

As microalbuminuria is cause for generalized atherosclerosis and also increased renal endothelial permeability, therefore it should be considered as biomarker of renal microvascular disease.

Acknowledgement: The authors would like to express their gratitude towards the hospital staffs of Agartala Government Medical College for their support and co-operation and goodwill throughout the study period. Authors remain ever thankful to the patients and volunteers for their kind co-operation and participation.

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